

D3.1 Offline deliberative process

TRANSFORM

Deliverable description

Deliverable:

D3.1 Offline Deliberative Process

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Summary.

This deliverable outlines the lessons learned from the offline deliberative process conducted in Lombardy in the framework of the EU H2020 TRANSFORM project, which took place in Lombardy (in Milan) in June 2022 in the shape of a Citizens' Jury.

The activities were coordinated, designed, and conducted by Giannino Bassetti Foundation, in dialogue with Lombardy Region, Directorate of Education, Universities, Research, Innovation and Simplification, and Finlombarda (the three organizations constituting the TRANSFORM Lombardy cluster).

The document aims at sharing the key understandings from this participatory experience that could be useful for policy makers and other interested actors willing to embark on citizen engagement actions based on deliberative methods for the design of research and innovation policies so as to be more aligned with citizens' needs and expectations.

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The context.

The main goal of TRANSFORM is to render regional policy making on research and innovation more open, responsible, and democratic by implementing citizens engagement actions. The project brings together three regions in Europe (Lombardy Region, Catalunya and Brussels-Capital Region), testing three different citizens' engagement methodologies (respectively, participatory research and innovation agenda setting, citizens' science and multi-stakeholder engagement).

Within the realm of TRANSFORM, Lombardy Region commits to render the regional Smart Specialization Strategy more inclusive and transparent, ensuring that citizens' voices are heard, and opinions taken into account when setting up key regional R&I policies.

The expected impacts of TRANSFORM in Lombardy are:

- Bringing the citizens views in the regional policies on research and innovation
- Testing deliberative tools within Lombardy framework
- Contributing to the institutional change of regional public administration - also beyond the Lombardy Region Unit engaged in TRANSFORM - in an RRI direction
- Contributing to the diffusion of the deliberative culture and practice
- Contributing to building trust among different stakeholders.

One of the primary objectives of the TRANSFORM project in Lombardy is to develop and test participatory methodologies to be used in the definition of the regional research and innovation agenda setting. The primary purpose of participatory research agenda setting methodologies, as the name suggests, is in fact to identify, together with the community involved (participatory), the priorities that should guide the policy planning (agenda setting) in the field of research and innovation (research).

As it was in the design of the previous regional strategic programs of Lombardy Region (Three-year Strategic Program for Research, Innovation and Technology Transfer-PST 2018-2020 and S3 Plan 2021-2027), the identification of citizens' needs, to which research and innovation try to provide answers with technological and knowledge solutions and options, plays a key role in the preparation of the new PST (2021-2023). Building on a

discussion and mutual learning process, the partners composing the Lombardy cluster of the project (Giannino Bassetti Foundation, FGB, coordinator of the project and of the Lombardy cluster, Lombardy Region and Finlombarda) decided to focus the first part of the citizen engagement activities within TRANSFORM on the identification of the citizens' needs.

The participatory process - designed by FGB in dialogue with Lombardy Region and Finlombarda, and with the support of project advisor Simon Burall (Involve) - was designed from Fall 2020 and took place in spring 2021 and included two phases: a survey (Annex I - Lombardy needs from the voices of citizens) and an online deliberative workshop dialogue (Annex II - Fair energy transition for all in Lombardy from the citizens' voice).

On the basis of the results of the survey, it was evident that the topics regarding the broader field of sustainability are a priority for Lombardy's citizens. For this reason, in selecting the focus of the deliberative workshop, it was decided to focus on this domain. Following a further discussion within the Lombardy cluster, the field of action has been restricted to the topic of Energy. Subsequently, the theme has been finalized with the subject "Fair energy transition for all" to combine technical and scientific aspects with social implications unavoidable in this context, to embrace the sustainability theme in a comprehensive way (also including its social dimension) and not only in a merely environmental sense.

The whole participatory process is described in [a specific section](#) within the Lombardy Region portal Open Innovation (in Italian).

The Citizens' Jury.

After the conclusion of the first part of the participatory research agenda setting exercise, which was considered successful from Lombardy Region who used the results to design the Three-year Strategic Program for Research, Innovation and Technology Transfer (2021-2023)¹, an extensive deliberative exercise structured as a Citizens' Jury was conceived, designed and implemented from October 2021 to June 2022.

A Citizens' Jury is “a method of deliberation developed by the Jefferson Center where a small group of people (between 12 and 24), representative of the demographics of a given area, come together to deliberate on an issue (generally one clearly framed question), over the period of 2 to 7 days” (from Involve website).

The aim of the Citizens' Jury was to collect citizens' recommendations on responsibility-related issues around regional smart (data-driven) mobility (Responsible Smart Mobility Citizens' Jury – Giuria di Cittadine e Cittadini su Mobilità Intelligente e Responsabile).

The topic was jointly selected by Fondazione Giannino Bassetti, Lombardy Region and Finlombarda, aiming at combining the technical aspects of smart mobility with its societal dimensions, so as to guarantee a comprehensive understanding of the topic when designing and implementing regional policies in the field. Another key factor considered to frame the Citizens' Jury was the regional policy framework and Lombardy Region's commitment in the implementation of innovative actions within the Regional Strategy on Smart Mobility and Artificial Intelligence. The regional Strategy on Smart Mobility and Artificial Intelligence describes four main streams of action, one of them being the “Connectivity/Data” area, which refers to “the possibility to share mobility-related information and data in an open manner able to grow over time”. Lombardy Region considers this topic as “one of the great game-changers in the life of territories, intended

¹ A full paragraph on TRANSFORM was inserted in the Plan to describe the project activities and how results have been used in the Plan (more information are retrievable here: <https://www.openinnovation.regione.lombardia.it/it/b/572/innovazione-via-libera-al-programma-strategico-triennale-da-miliardi>).

to facilitate the management of public mobility services by creating environments that are favorable for experimenting innovation”.

A key innovative tool promoted by Lombardy Region to experiment and foster the development of innovative data-driven services, including smart mobility, is the [E015 platform](#). This initiative consists of a digital ecosystem, which allows public and private players operating in the territory to share open sets of data.

With the interventions through the Citizens’ Jury, Lombardy Region would have liked to integrate its forthcoming actions and initiatives in the field of artificial intelligence and mobility (e.g., funding programs, strategic documents and initiatives, etc.) with the citizens’ recommendations, ensuring a responsible and open approach to the governance of data-driven innovation by taking into account the value-related reflections collected directly from Lombardy residents’ voices.

The Citizens’ Jury was conducted on June 11th and 25th, 2022 in Milan. The duration of the Jury was 14 hours total (10:30 am- 5.30pm), with a one-hour lunch break and two mid-morning and mid-afternoon 15 minutes breaks for the two days.

A sample of 24 citizens residing in Lombardy participated in the Citizens’ Jury, selected randomly but stratified by gender, province of residence and age. Other socio-economic criteria (i.e., education and income) were also considered in the recruiting stage. The size of the province had determined the presence of more people from some provinces.

Obviously, the small sample of participants recruited for the Jury cannot be considered representative of the entire Lombardy population. However, the diversity of voices reached by balancing the selection starting from the parameters listed above ensured the presence of diverse, heterogenous experiences, values, and views, which are essential for a successful deliberative process.

The recruitment of the 24 citizens was carried out by an agency specialized in marketing and opinion research (Istituto Piepoli). The same agency, in the costs of the service, has

included a monetary incentive (given through supermarket coupons) to the participants as well as the coverage of travel expenses to reach the venue of the Citizens' Jury.

The structure of the process was the typical one of the deliberative processes:

- Informative phase
- Dialogue phase
- Deliberative phase

The activities alternated moments of plenary discussion, moderated by a main facilitator, with moments of dialogue in 3 smaller groups of 8 people (through breakout rooms), always moderated by a facilitator. The groups were each time re-sorted to allow a wider sharing of perspectives among all participants.

The first day (11th June 2022) was entirely devoted to the informative phase. In a first session, participants were introduced to the scope of the Jury, to the Lombardy Region framework on smart mobility and data driven services, and to the citizens' role in the process. In the remaining part of the day, the jurors listened to and interacted with independent experts on Big Data and AI, Open Data, Smart Mobility, Privacy, Inclusion and Gender Equality in the data domain. All experts were selected by Giannino Bassetti Foundation.

The dialogue and the deliberative phase happened in the second day. The discussion was structured in three breakout sessions and plenaries. In the first block of activities citizens identified the key responsibility related issues around smart, data-driven mobility, which mainly led to reflections on privacy and profiling, inclusion, accessibility, security, and safety. In the second part of the day, citizens collectively elaborate a first draft of the recommendations for Lombardy Region. In the final part of the day the recommendations were refined and then presented to two representatives from Lombardy Region that were invited to join this very last session for a formal "delivery" of the recommendations from the jurors to the regional authority.

At the end a questionnaire to evaluate the experience from the participants' perspective was distributed and filled out by the citizens involved.

A full report of the results of the Citizens' Jury (which is not the main focus of this deliverable) will be elaborated and discussed with Lombardy Region in due time.

Lessons learned.

Benefits and value of deliberative processes

The deliberative processes, if a Citizen's Jury, a Citizens' Assembly or a Citizens' Panel, bring several advantages, that definitely have been the main reason why Lombardy Region decided to embark on TRANSFORM and to select participatory research agenda setting as the approach to be implemented in the region. The high-value of such methods and the full awareness that these exercises are not so diffused in Italy were at the basis of the decision for the Lombardy Cluster to translate in Italian the OECD report ["Innovative Citizen Participation and New Democratic Institutions: Catching the Deliberative Wave"](#) (Highlights 2020)² which, among many other things like providing a solid guide and listing fundamental principles and practices of public deliberation, comprehensively illustrates the advantages of deliberations, which constitute the first and major lesson learned from the offline deliberative process held in 2022 in Lombardy for the regional authority involved.

According to the OECD report, benefits of deliberation are:

- Better policy outcomes because deliberation results in considered public judgements rather than public opinions;
- Greater legitimacy to make hard choices;
- Enhance public trust in government and democratic institutions by giving citizens an effective role in public decision making;
- Signal civic respect and empower citizens;
- Make governance more inclusive by opening the door to a much more diverse group of people;
- Strengthen integrity and prevent corruption by ensuring that groups and individuals with money and power cannot have undue influence on a public decision;

² The Italian translation of the Highlights 2020 of the OECD report ["Innovative Citizen Participation and New Democratic Institutions: Catching the Deliberative Wave"](#) was presented online on 25th October 2021. The launch event, named from the translated report "Innovazione nella partecipazione dei cittadini al decision making pubblico e nuove istituzioni democratiche. Cavalcare l'onda della deliberazione", will take place online from 3 to 5 pm on the Zoom platform.

The contents of the report will be presented by Alessandro Bellantoni, Head of the Open Government and Civic Space Unit of the OECD. The event will provide also the opportunity to dialogue with experts in and policy makers experiencing public deliberation: Ângela Guimarães Pereira (Joint Research Center, Ispra – European Commission), Caterina Cittadini (National Commission for Public Debate – Italian Ministry of Sustainable Infrastructure and Mobility), Enza Cristofaro (Directorate General for Education, University, Research, Innovation and Simplification – Lombardy Region), and Daniela Ferrara (General Directorate for the Economy of Knowledge, Labor and Business – Emilia-Romagna Region). The event will be introduced and moderated by Angela Simone, coordinator of TRANSFORM and Lombardy Cluster leader.

- Help counteract polarisation and disinformation.

Practical tips

The grounding of a Citizens' Jury, as well as other deliberative methods, could be complex, depending on the level of knowledge, maturity and practice in the institutional context in which the deliberative exercise will be embedded. Procedural constraints can heavily affect the good implementation of the methodology or at least could entail more effort and time in develop a proper process. Furthermore, preparation of key actors and material in the process needs to be carefully considered so as to produce high-quality results that are meaningful for the involved citizens and actionable by the committed public authority

Knowing in advance what could be the bottlenecks that can be turned into opportunities might help potential organizers to plan correctly timing, procedures and phases, before overpromising implementation and results to the public authority interested to set the exercise or publicly launching the process.

Here following some of the practical hurdles, that we have encountered in the making, from which we have learnt, and that we suggest to take into account in a potential design and setting up of a Citizens' Jury:

- *Civic lottery vs. recruiting agency*

Having randomly selected citizens is an essential part of the Jury since can guarantee to gather all kind of views, perspectives and then recommendations, avoiding the collection of suggestions just from the "usual suspects" (people already interested in that topic or willing to participate in this type of exercise whatever the topic is or even worst engaged for vested interests). To run an ideal civic lottery the institution in charge of promoting the deliberative process needs to store and process or at least access citizens' data at population level. These datasets are not available at any level (local, regional, national, etc.) since the collection or processing – even more after the EU General Data Protection Regulation – is permitted only for a specific reason (elections, health system needs, etc). In our specific case, also because it was the first experience in implementing a Citizens' Jury and the first attempt of using a civic lottery in Lombardy (and so there was no procedure in place for such purpose of inhabitants data processing), it was not possible for Lombardy Region to access citizens' data in the region and deploy a civic lottery to randomly select citizens. In principle, this procedure

is not impossible to be run but requires time and a joint effort of different departments in the Region to obtain these datasets and implement a proper Civic Lottery. The alternative – used in the TRANSFORM case – was to select citizens through a recruiting agency (specialized in qualitative research) to guarantee anyway a random distribution and a fair representativeness of the variety in the group to be part of the Jury, according to the criteria requested. Even if considered a more narrow and - by some scholars and practitioners of deliberative democracy - less robust approach, the agency selection can provide some advantages to some extent. Because of the GDPR, personal data processing – especially in case of sensitive data – is not easy and very often public authority cannot “profile” citizens according to specific features (e.g. census) and this can affect a proper representation of the population in the “mini-public” for the deliberative process. Thus, even if civic lottery is a golden standard, further reflections on how to complement this approach to have a full representativeness in the Jury is needed.

→ Civic lottery is the golden standard but don't deny citizens recruitment through an agency or combined methods to ensure a broad representativeness in the mini-public.

- *Actions during the Jury and actions before and in between of the Jury's appointments.*
Even if the most part of the Jury obviously unfolds during the events in person, communications before and in between of the Jury's appointments are really important both to set the stage and to reinforce information or provide more material that can be requested by the jurors. Especially in shorter Citizens' Juries (two-days long, as in our case) in which there is no much time to go extensively through information and discussion with the experts, communications in preparation of or after the first event are relevant to exploit the time in person for dialogue and deliberation and to complement the information phase with further in depth or on demand material.
→ Use properly the time in preparation of and in between of the Jury's meetings to provide information and material

- *“Witness experts” selection and briefing*
Selecting the right experts for the informative phase is key but this could require time. And even if you are able to prepare the perfect list of the experts in line with your topic,

they could be not available in the days of the Jury. Furthermore, even if experienced in delivering presentations to peers or stakeholders, they could be less prepared to provide good speeches for the general public. Thus planning several briefing with them and preparing a list of suggestions on how to handle a public presentation, as done in our case, could be really useful to avoid “surprising” contents during the Jury events.

→ Dedicate enough time to select and brief the witness experts since their contents will be relevant for the framing of the dialogue and recommendations preparation.

- *R&I ecosystem actors as witness experts*

In the case of the participatory research agenda setting exercise in TRANSFORM, the process is in integral part of the design of regional strategic programs, like S3, which are typically conceived together with R&I ecosystems stakeholders (e.g. through the so-called Entrepreneurial Discovery Process – EDP). Such introduction of deliberative process and lay experts voices (namely the citizens) can be not well perceived by R&I ecosystem stakeholders. Explaining them the process but above all including some of them in the informative part is a way to provide them with first-hand experience that can foster their buy-in and support (or even enthusiasm, as in the case of Lombardy) so as to transform and enlarge the co-design processes for strategic regional R&I policies and plans.

→ Exploit deliberative approaches to create Societal Discovery Processes for strategic regional R&I policies and plans.

- *Recommendations as a way to read regional societal attitudes and awareness*

The main outcomes of the deliberative processes are the recommendations formulated by the citizens part of the Jury, but contents of the recommendations, apart from providing suggestions to guide local policymaking, can provide information on societal attitude or even knowledge about specific issues. For instance, in the case of our Citizens’ Jury, many recommendations insisted on data protection and how to ensure that citizens are protected by potential misuse and abuse of their personal data. Most of these citizens’ requests are already regulated as key elements in the GDPR. Thus, this means that there is no diffused awareness of the GDPR tool as a way to protect citizens’ interests and rights. As a consequence, the public authority can invest on

public courses and communication campaigns about the GDPR – also in conjunction with national authorities devoted to this theme - but can also reflect upon public perception – and perhaps potential controversy – on some technology because citizens believe there is a lack of public control on this topic. Thus, a deeper analysis of the recommendations beyond the primary meaning of those suggestions is advisable and provide a further level of benefit stemming from the implementation of such processes.

→ Read through the recommendations to capture societal perception, attitudes and knowledge to prevent potential innovation controversies.

Annex I - Lombardy needs from the voices of citizens

The citizens engagement path in the regional research agenda setting

Survey Results

Edited by Fondazione Giannino Bassetti

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1. Background

One of the primary objectives of the TRANSFORM project in Lombardy is to develop and test participatory methodologies to be used in the definition of the regional research and innovation agenda setting. The primary purpose of participatory research agenda setting methodologies, as the name suggests, is in fact to identify, together with the community involved (participatory), the priorities that should guide the policy planning (agenda setting) in the field of research and innovation (research).

As it was in the design of the previous regional strategic programs of Lombardy Region (Three-year Strategic Program for Research, Innovation and Technology Transfer-PST 2018-2020 and S3 Plan 2021-2027), the identification of citizens' needs, to which research and innovation try to provide answers with technological and knowledge solutions and options, plays a key and primary role in the preparation of the new PST (2021-2023).

Building on a discussion and mutual learning process, the partners composing the Lombardy cluster of the project (Giannino Bassetti Foundation, FGB, coordinator of the project and of the Lombardy cluster, Lombardy Region and Finlombarda) have decided to focus the first part of the citizen engagement activities within TRANSFORM on the identification of the citizens' needs.

The participatory process - designed by FGB in dialogue with Lombardy Region and Finlombarda, and with the support of project advisor Simon Burall (Involve) - took place in spring 2021 and included two phases: a survey, whose preliminary results are shortly described in this report, and an online deliberative dialogue (May 2021).

2. Methodological note

The questionnaire, designed by Giannino Bassetti Foundation in dialogue with Lombardy Region and Finlombarda, was administered to a sample of 1002 people. The sample, representative of Lombardy population, was composed of adults (more than 18 years old) living in Lombardy and calibrated by age (*Figure 1*), gender (*Figure 2*) and province of residence (*Figure 3*).

Figure 1 – Composition of the sample: age

Figure 2 – Composition of the sample: sex

Figure 3 – Composition of the sample: province of residence

During the interview phase, additional socio-demographic information were also collected (section I), such as the type of residence area (urban/suburban/rural/none of these – *Figure 4*), the size of the family unites (*Figure 5*), the presence in the family unit of people over 60 years old, under 14 years old and non-self-sufficient (*Figure 6*).

Figure 4 – Socio-demographic variables: area of residence

Figure 5 – Socio-demographic variables: number of household members

Figure 6 – Socio-demographic variables: presence in the household of people over 70 years old, under 14 years of age and non-self-sufficient people.

The survey was administered between April 20 and April 28 (2021) through both CATI (Computer Assisted Telephone Interview) and CAWI (Computer Assisted Web Interview) methodologies to diversify the access to the survey. The goal was to broaden the participation to different segments of the population, guaranteeing that the sample was truly representative of citizens in Lombardy.

The questionnaire, consisting of 15 questions, was divided into 4 sections:

- I. *General information* (General socio-personal information)
- II. *The needs of the Lombardy territory* (Needs perceived by respondents in relation to the Lombardy territory)
- III. *The needs of Lombardy citizens* (Needs of the interviewees with reference to their household)
- IV. *Designing research and innovation priorities in Lombardy* (Which territorial actors should Lombardy Region engage when shaping its R&I strategies).

The survey was designed keeping in mind the descriptions and categories of needs that were identified in the prior regional strategic programs on research and innovation, to try to gather information that could be fully used by Regione Lombardia and Finlombarda in the definition of the PST 2021-2023.

In the sampling and administration activities, FGB was supported by an external agency specialized in research and opinion polls (SWG).

3. The objectives of the Lombardy territory

In the set of questions collected in Section II, participants were asked to indicate what they thought were the most urgent goals for Lombardy territory. The objectives presented in the questionnaire are the result of a reworking and contextualization of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the United Nations 2030 Agenda - parameters widely used in regional planning policies in Lombardy and thus also present in the current S3 (2021-2027) and in the PST 2018-2020 – based on the peculiarities of Lombardy.

The list of objectives used in the questionnaire:

- Less people in absolute poverty
- More people getting enough food on a regular basis
- More people accessing quality food
- More people living in good health and well-being (in terms of health)
- More children and young people with quality school education
- Gender equality (e.g., so that women can hold senior roles in companies or institutions as well as men; so that women can receive the same salary of male colleagues working in the same position)
- More people using clean, safe water for food and personal care
- More people having access to clean energy (for heating, food preparation, cooling) at sustainable prices
- More people with decent jobs
- Better mobility infrastructure (railways, roads, etc.)
- More and better services to support marginalized or disadvantaged groups (e.g., people with physical or mental disabilities, immigrants)
- Less pollution impacts of cities
- More responsible consumption and production (to avoid waste and the release of pollutants)
- More actions to fight climate change

- More actions to safeguard biodiversity (conservation of different species of plants and animals in the territory)

We would like to stress that, in general, all the objectives listed were found to strongly correspond to the demands and needs of Lombardy's citizens. Indeed, when asked to answer to the question "How much is each of the listed objectives an objective for the Lombardy region and its citizens?" more than 9 out of 10 people (910 out of 1002 interviewees) answered "very much" or "much" for at least one of the proposed needs (on a scale that included as options "very much", "much", "partially", "a little", "not at all").

This outcome is clearly relevant because it shows that the development of the 8 innovation ecosystems, which are present in both the prior PST (2018-2020) and in the current S3 plan, as frameworks within which to develop responses to needs, is consistent with the actual needs directly described by citizens. If in previous regional R&I programmatic plans, citizens' needs were assumed from reports and different experiences made by regional policymakers, the involvement of a representative sample of Lombardy citizens, which took place thanks to the TRANSFORM project, clearly marks that those needs are present and strongly perceived as priorities for the Lombardy territory. This evidence traces a path of continuity, should the ecosystems also be used in the drafting of the PST 2021-2023, at the same time providing the regional policy makers with the awareness that there is a correspondence between the needs described in the strategic documents and the opinions of citizens.

Going into detail, most respondents identified the following three priority goals:

- 1. More children and young people with a quality school education (66%)**
- 2. More people with decent jobs (65%)**
- 3. Less pollution impacts of cities (62%)**

Below are all of the objectives, ordered by priority, based on the percentage of citizens who, when asked about the importance of the goals themselves, responded "very much" or "much" (*Figure 7*):

Figure 7 – The objectives for the Lombardy area: "much" and "very much" answers

➔ One fact that emerges with some degree of emphasis, concerns the category of objectives most directly linked to environmental sustainability³, for which younger people (18-24 years old) seem to be more sensitive, along with - in part - older people (over 65).

In assigning these priorities, characterizations are observed based on recorded socio-demographic variables.

In general, young people (up to 24) and older people (over 65) attributed more importance to the following goals:

- Young people, especially with regard to the education, disadvantaged people, sustainable infrastructure and in general for the environment and climate change;
- the elderly regarding the environment and nutrition (see Annex 2 - Age).

³ List of objectives considered related to "sustainability": More responsible consumption and production; Infrastructure for mobility; More people using clean and safe water for food and personal care; More actions to protect biodiversity; More people having access to clean energy at sustainable prices; More actions to fight climate change; Less pollution impacts of cities.

Quality education is particularly relevant in the younger (18-24) and older (over 65) age ranges. In these categories the rate of those who responded "very much" or "much" rises to 73% and 70%, respectively. Differences in percentages are also registered in the various areas of residence (the percentage in rural areas rises to 69%) and above all in the different provinces (Sondrio and Monza and Brianza at one extreme and Varese at the other) (see Attachment 2 - Provinces).

Men tended to have a higher inclination to select the objective "Fewer people in absolute poverty" and "More actions to fight climate change", while women showed higher sensitiveness for the objective "More people with access to quality food" (see Attachment 2 - Gender).

Considering the number of people in the respondent's household, it is quite evident that people living alone tend to answer "very much" and "much" more frequently than the other categories (household consisting of 2, 3, 4 or more than 4 people), with the sole exception of four needs:

- More children and young people with quality education (more frequent among people in a 4-person household);
- More people using clean, safe water for food and personal care (more frequent among people in a 4-person household);
- More and better services to support marginalized or disadvantaged groups (more frequent among people in a 2- and 4-person household);
- Less pollution impacts of cities (more frequent among people who are part of a 3- and 4-person household).

Another element that seems to have an influence on the citizens perception around the importance of certain challenges is the presence in the respondent's household of a non-self-sufficient person: the rate of those who answered "very much + much" is in fact lower among those who must deal with non-self-sufficient people in the household on all the listed needs.

The impact of Covid

Respondents were also asked to provide their views on the impact that the Covid-19 pandemic has had on the objectives listed in the interview. According to respondents, education, health, and work were the three areas most impacted by the health emergency. The shift in priorities is shown in Table 1:

Table 1 – The objectives for the Lombardy territory: in general, and following Covid-19

Women indicate more strongly than men three objectives: "More people with access to clean, affordable energy," "More children and young people with quality education," and "More people accessing quality food" (see Exhibit 2 - Gender).

Overall, young people (18-24 years old and 25-34 years old) did not express greater urgency about achieving the goals under Covid-19, while those over 65 identify more - compared to the average response - with goals related to food, responsible consumption and production, access to water, pollution, and gender equality (see Annex 2 - Age).

According to citizens living in the provinces of Como, Lecco and Sondrio, Covid-19 had a significant impact on most of the objectives, whilst residents in the provinces of Cremona, Mantua and Lodi showed an opposite view (see Annex 2 - Provinces). The impact of COVID-19 is most often pointed out by people in large households (more than four people) regarding all the needs, with the exceptions of "more people with decent jobs" and "better mobility infrastructure (rail, roads, etc.)" (*Figure 8*). This finding seems to indicate a greater impact of the pandemic on larger households.

Figure 8 – COVID's impact on territorial challenges.

4. Priorities of the Lombardy region

When asked to choose just two priority goals, respondents overall suggested jobs, health, education, and tackling poverty.

Below are the percentages for the first - *Figure 9* - and second choice - *Figure 10*, respectively.

First priority:

1. More people with decent jobs (20%)
2. More people living in good health and well-being (in terms of health) (19%)
3. More children and young people with a quality school education (14%)

Figure 9 – Lombardy citizens' priorities: first choice

The priorities described vary in relation to the sociodemographic variables identified.

In particular, in selecting the first priority, men are more likely than women to indicate "More people with decent job", while the opposite occurs for "More people living in health and

wellbeing" and "More children and young people with quality school education". Considering the age of the respondents, a significant difference emerges with respect to the "job" priority, with young people up to 24 expressing less attention to the issue than the average respondent and especially compared to those in the 51-65 age group.

A substantial homogeneity is recorded by analyzing the responses of the respondents subdivided according to their place of residence. Those who live in the areas of Lodi and Mantua emphasize work as a priority, while residents of Sondrio, Lodi and Mantua, unlike those in Lecco, emphasize health and well-being. The priority of "education" is highly felt in Cremona, less so in Bergamo (see Attachment 2 - Priorities). Respondents belonging to larger households (more than 4 persons) gave significantly greater weight to the following needs:

- "Gender equality," with +9 percentage points above average;
- "More people living in health and well-being (in terms of health)," with +7 percentage points above average.

The need for "More and better services to support marginalized or disadvantaged categories (e.g., persons with physical or mental disabilities, immigrants)" becomes a more frequent priority in the presence of persons who are not self-sufficient (+6 percentage points with respect to the average). It is also recorded how the presence of "Better infrastructures for mobility" is instead less important for those who live with a person over 70 (+3 percentage points over the average).

Second priority:

1. More people with decent jobs (15%)
2. More children with quality school education (13%)
3. Fewer people in absolute poverty (9%)

*Figure 10 – Lombardy citizens' priorities: second choice
[4% of respondents indicated only the first priority].*

Focusing the analysis on the third objective indicated as the second priority, i.e. "Fewer people in absolute poverty", it can be seen that it is men and the people that fall in the age ranges 51-65 and over 65 that are most sensitive. The same occurs for residents of the provinces of Como, Sondrio, Brescia, Cremona and Lodi (see Attachment 2 - Priorities).

It is also reported that:

- the needs "More people living in health and well-being" and "More people with access to clean, affordable energy" are more prevalent among the suburban population (+22 and +16 percentage points above average, respectively);
- the need "More children and young people with a quality school education" is more prevalent in households of more than 4 people (+9 percentage points above average);
- the need "More people with decent jobs" is more prevalent among people living in rural areas (+3 percentage points);
- people living with people with disabilities, on the other hand, are more responsive to the needs "More and better services to support marginalized groups" (+3% above average) and "More people with access to clean, affordable energy" (+4% above average).

- "Gender equality" is more strongly felt in households where a child under 14 is present than in households where children are not present (+4%).

5. Responses to the priorities of the Lombardy territory

After selecting the territory's two most pressing priorities, respondents were asked to comment on possible responses to solve the selected target. Improving **public policies and services** was identified as the most effective action to help achieve the territory's objectives, followed by **listening to and involving citizens**.

The rate of citizens assigning an important role to the results from the world of research and innovation (public, private, or the result of public-private collaborations) to respond to the priorities identified are notable (between 56% and 49%), but they rank behind other solutions and actions that are considered more relevant, such as regional and national/international public policies, citizen involvement, improvement of people's lifestyles and correct public information.

This finding is perfectly in line with the criticism of the so-called technological fix, that is the tendency to overestimate the role of technology in responding to "high" needs, such as the challenges of society, which cannot be solved with merely technological answers. When asked to answer to the question "Let's list some actions below. How much would each of them contribute to achieving the goal (insert/quote first goal by priority)?", participants responded as below (sum of "much" and "very much" responses for the first - *Figure 11* - and second priority - *Figure 12*, respectively).

First priority:

1. Better regional public policies (laws, penalties, incentives) (66%)
2. Better national or international public policies (63%)
Better public services (social services, mobility services, etc.) (63%)
3. Listening to and involving citizens (58%)

Figure 11 – "Much" and "very much" responses related to actions to address Lombard citizens' first priority [respondent base 910].

Second priority:

1. Better regional public policies (laws, penalties, incentives) (69%)
2. Better national or international public policies (65%)
Better public services (social services, mobility services, etc.) (65%)
3. Listening to and involving citizens (62%)

Figure 12 – "Much" and "very much" responses related to actions to address Lombard citizens' second priority
[respondent base 874].

In general, young people up to 24 years of age show greater confidence in reference to the answers listed (see Attachment 2 - Age), while men and women do not express significantly different positions. Women tend to indicate more often the need of public policies (when research and innovation are indicated as solutions to answer to the first need selected) and not to limit themselves to the technological response alone (in reference to the second priority) (see Attachment 2 - Gender).

Overall, the citizens living in the provinces of Lodi and Sondrio show higher levels of confidence in the answers listed than those who reside in the provinces of Brescia, Pavia, Cremona, Mantua and Lecco (see Attachment 2 - Provinces).

The actions indicated by participants to address the priorities selected as most urgent differ by goal.

➔ One fact that emerges clearly is that **listening to and involving citizens** is perceived as a **particularly relevant** action to respond to some of the **challenges directly related to environmental sustainability** (sum of "much" and "very much" responses):

- More responsible consumption and production (83%)
- More actions to protect biodiversity (83%)
- More people accessing clean water (79%)
- More people accessing clean energy (77%)

When participants were asked to openly provide their comments and suggestions (through open-ended questions) around actions that could help achieving goals they identified as priorities - in addition to **health**, with a strong emphasis on requests for improvement and extension of territorial health - **quality school education** was confirmed as a crucial issue, in a twofold perspective (see Figure 13).

Figure 13 – Representation of the categories to which the actions described by participants to address the goals they identified as priorities can be attributed (open-ended responses)

On the one hand, many participants highlighted the importance of greater investment and/or intervention in **schools**, in both **facilities** and **access to services**:

"Create classrooms where you can study even outside school hours, with computer systems for those who don't have them";

"We should organize the school much better; keep classrooms in order, etc.";

"More funding for public schools";

"Kindergarten at capped prices";

"Access to university";

On the other, respondent attention focused on **teachers**:

"Better teachers' selection and quality programs - computer science in elementary schools and more English".

"Ensuring quality standards for teachers through scores given by families".

On the other hand, the school, and more generally the sphere of **education**, has been identified as ideal means to sensitize the population on various issues, from attention to the environment to encouraging a sense of civic duty:

"Fostering education to respect the environment and stimulate the fight against waste of all kinds since kindergarten";

"Raising awareness of nurseries and kindergartens for proper nutrition";

"Educating young people to solidarity".

In suggesting some actions to achieve the identified priority goals, participants held themselves to different levels of detail. In some cases, they provided very specific elements, demonstrating an in-depth knowledge on the issues proposed and a significant capacity to envisioning potential governance tools that could be adopted in response to those needs. Sometimes citizens also provided specific examples and best practices, confirming themselves as key actors not only in the identification of needs, but also for the development of potential responses to the challenges identified.

For example, in order to promote **gender equality**, participants gave fairly pointed guidance:

"Incentives for companies with gender parity."

"Mandatory leave for fathers. Tax incentives to companies that achieve adequate levels of gender equality and activate corporate welfare services for men and women".

Or, in the case of **mobility infrastructure**:

"Specifically with regard to the environment, one could follow the example of Tallinn ("free" public transportation, i.e., paid for with taxes). Paid only by tourists <https://www.lastampa.it/motori/ambiente/2018/06/05/news/autobus-gratis-l-estonia-sara-il-primo-paese-a-rendere-gratuito-il-trasporto-pubblico-1.34022191>";

"Improvement of public transport and lowering the price of tickets";

"An enhancement of public transportation with shorter but accessible lines".

 Also, with respect to actions to promote **energy transition** and **environmental sustainability**, citizens have provided concrete and specific suggestions:

"Create multiple points for distribution of expiring or expired food";

"Economic benefits for green technologies and quantified environmental cost included in the price of items/food";

"Create municipal or regional funds for installation of photovoltaic panels. Create energy communities. Make municipal water, electricity and gas supply tenders."

6. The most urgent needs of Lombardy's citizens

The third section of the survey focused on the personal and family needs of citizens. When asked to identify if a series of needs were important (yes/no), participants responded as below (rate of "Yes" - *Figure 14*):

1. Prevent disease (87%)
2. Live in safe environments and settings (85%)
3. Have easy-to-use citizen services (e.g., registry office, school enrollments, medical reservations) (83%)
Safe mobility (as a pedestrian, cyclist, motorist) (83%)

Figure 14 – Responses related to the personal and family needs of citizens [respondent base: 1002].

When asked to identify **two priority needs**, participants emphasized the importance of **health (prevention and community healthcare), work, and safety**, responding as follows (percentage values for the first and second priorities, respectively - see *Figure 15* for a summary of responses that considers both the first and second needs):

First need:

1. **Prevent diseases (20%)**
2. **Work safely and with a decent salary (18%)**
3. **Receive timely and appropriate care close to home (15%)**
4. Live in safe environments and settings (11%)
5. Receive innovative treatments and therapies (7%)
6. Have quality food in sufficient quantity (4%)
Have easy-to-use services for citizens (e.g. registry office, school enrollments, medical reservations) (4%)
Tackle violence against women, homosexuals and transgender people (gender-based violence) (4%)
7. Receive treatment or rehabilitation at home whenever possible (3%)
Move by efficient and non-polluting public transport (3%)
Ensure the protection and inclusion in society of minorities and vulnerable people (e.g. people with disabilities) (3%)
8. Enhance one's growth through culture and the arts (2%)
Have access to quality information (2%)
Move on safe roads (as a pedestrian, cyclist, motorist) (2%)
9. Communicate effectively with one's personal contacts or for school or work reasons (1%)
Live well among different cultures (multiculturalism) (1%)

The analysis of the feedback collected based on the socio-demographic profile of respondents does not reveal strong differences. However, it can be observed that women seem to have higher levels of needs regarding health-related needs, while men with respect to job (see Attachment 2 - Gender); young people and adults up to 50 years also tend to privilege job-related needs (see Attachment 2 - Age). With respect to the needs "Working safely and with a decent salary" and "Receiving timely and adequate care close to home" residents of the provinces of Sondrio, Bergamo, Pavia and Lodi had a higher degree of responses, while Milan was in contrast to this trend.

Second need:

1. **Work safely and with a decent salary (16%)**
2. **Live in safe environments and settings (11%)**
3. **Receive timely and appropriate care close to home (10%)**
4. Prevent diseases (8%)
5. Receive innovative treatments and therapies (7%)
6. Enhance one' s growth through culture and art (6%)
Have easy-to-use services for citizens (e.g., registry office, school enrollment, medical reservations) (6%)
7. Move on safe roads (as a pedestrian, cyclist, motorist) (5%)
Move by efficient and non-polluting public transport (5%)
Live well among different cultures (multiculturalism) (5%)
8. Have quality food in sufficient quantity (4%)
Receive treatment or rehabilitation at home, whenever possible (4%)
Ensure the protection and inclusion in society of minorities and vulnerable people (e.g. people with disabilities) (4%)
Tackle violence against women, homosexuals and transgender people (gender-based violence) (4%)
9. Communicate effectively with one's personal contacts or for school or work reasons (2%)
Have access to quality information (2%)

Figure 15 – Priorities related to citizens' personal and family needs (sum of first and second needs)

[Respondent base: 970 *2]

Free responses from citizens who were asked if they had additional personal or family needs to report mostly focused on (Figure 16):

- security and fight against crime;
- simplification of bureaucratic processes;
- environmental actions and incentives (and demand of penalties for those who violate the law).

Figure 16 - Word cloud representation of the categories to which the additional needs described by participants can be attributed (open-ended responses)

7. Research and innovation as tools for responding to the needs of Lombardy's citizens

In the context of personal and family needs, it was then asked whether research and innovation could address the needs identified as priorities (responses: yes/no/partially/not sure - *Figure 17*).

According to the Lombardy citizens interviewed, **research and innovation** are perceived to be **crucial** as:

- instruments that can provide responses to identified needs - the response was “yes” in 68% and 67% of cases (respectively, for the first and for the second need identified as priority);
- instruments that can provide partial responses to identified needs – the response was “partially” in 23% and 25% of cases (respectively, for the first and for the second need identified as priority).

Figure 17 – How much research and innovation can provide answers to identified needs (average first and second needs)

Research and innovation are identified as potentially relevant solutions primarily in the medical domain - namely to "prevent diseases" (no answer "no"), "receive timely and appropriate care close to home", "receive treatment or rehabilitation at home whenever possible", "receive innovative treatments and therapies"-, "move by efficient and non-polluting public transport", "have easy-to-use services for citizens (e.g. registry office, school enrolment, medical reservations), "enhance one's growth through culture and art", "have access to quality information".

On the other hand, the following needs seem to be less relevant (higher percentages of "no" responses): "have quality food in sufficient quantity", "live well among different cultures" and "tackle violence against women, homosexuals and transgender people".

Where research and innovation are identified as important tools for responding to the needs of the territory, the main reasons are that they "attract both public and private investment and resources to address that" (35%) and that they "provide concrete answers and/or solutions to the need" (Figure 18).

Figure 18 - How can research and innovation provide answers to identified needs?

Where technology is identified as partially solving or not solving the needs, the most frequently chosen reasons were "because a technological response alone would not fully solve the problem", "because meeting the need requires better behaviors and/or lifestyles of people", "because better public policies (e.g., laws, strategic plans, penalties, incentives) are needed to meet the need" (percentages between 28% and 20% - *Figure 19*).

Figura 19 - Why can't research and innovation provide answers to identified needs?

8. Designing research and innovation policies: the actors that need to be involved

The fourth section of the survey focused on the types of actors to be involved in the design of the Lombardy Region's research and innovation policies (*Figure 20*), which, according to the interviewees, should dialogue with:

1. Universities and research centers (43%)
2. Government (40%)
3. Citizens (37%)
4. Municipalities (35%)
5. Businesses (28%)
European Union (28%)
6. Professional associations and scientific societies (23%)
7. Citizens' associations (e.g. consumer associations, rights associations, environmental associations, etc.) (22%)
8. Third sector (e.g. associations, foundations, non-profit/non-profit organizations) (15%)
Other Italian regions (15%)

Figure 20 – Who should Lombardy Region talk to in order to define its research and innovation policies?

It is interesting to note how, together with the subjects that could most commonly be identified as key actors - the universities and the central government - the interviewees respond by recalling the role that the citizens themselves can play, together with those administrative bodies that are typically perceived close to the local communities: the municipalities (even though their role in regional R&I programming is not primary).

What is striking is the data referring to young people up to 24 years of age, who emphasized the importance of the role of the University and the Government if compared to other proposed actors, while men emphasized, alongside the universities, the importance of engaging professional associations and Third sector (see Attachment 2 - Gender and Age). Analyzing the responses by province, the picture is not homogeneous (see Attachment 2 - Provinces). People living in Sondrio and Lodi provinces present a higher rate of trust towards the proposed list of actors, while Cremona citizens place at the opposite side of the spectrum.

There are also some differences between urban/suburban/rural areas. For people living in urban areas, the European Union (+5 percentage points compared to the average) and the national government (+6 percentage points compared to the average) are more important. At the same time, it is quite evident that the third sector is indicated more often as a key stakeholder by participants who live in suburban areas (+4% with respect to the average), as well as by participants who live in a household with a non-self-sufficient person (+4% with respect to the average). Municipalities are preferred actors for those living in rural areas (+3% compared to average), while citizen engagement is indicated less often by those living in suburban areas (-3% compared to average).

Finally, we underline the **minor role attributed to businesses** and to the **European Union**, even though they are fundamental actors for the regional research and innovation system (in terms of financing and priorities - European Community - and obviously implementation of innovation actions - businesses). The limited focus (only one question) on the topic in this questionnaire does not allow for further analysis, but it could, however, open to a reflection on the issue. Further investigation is needed to understand if the outcome

described is the result of a knowledge gap that could be filled by providing citizens with better information around the regional system on research and innovation, its key players and their relative roles.

Annex II - Fair energy transition for all in Lombardy from the citizens' voice

The citizens engagement path in the regional research agenda setting

Deliberative workshop results

Edited by Fondazione Giannino Bassetti

16th July 2021

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1. **Background**

Building on a discussion and mutual learning process, the partners composing the Lombardy cluster of the project (Giannino Bassetti Foundation, FGB, coordinator of the project and of the Lombardy cluster, Lombardy Region and Finlombarda) have decided to focus the first part of the citizen engagement activities within TRANSFORM on the identification of the citizens' needs.

The participatory process - designed by FGB in dialogue with Lombardy Region and Finlombarda, and with the support of project advisor Simon Burall (Involve) - took place in spring 2021 and included two phases: a survey and an online deliberative dialogue, the last being the subject of this report.

Based on the results of the survey, it was evident that the topics regarding the broader field of sustainability were a priority for Lombardy's citizens. For this reason, in selecting the focus of the deliberative workshop, it was decided to focus on this domain. Following a further discussion within among the Lombardy cluster, the field of action has been restricted to the topic of Energy. Subsequently, the theme has been finalized with the subject "Fair energy transition for all" to combine technical and scientific aspects with social implications unavoidable in this context, to embrace the sustainability theme in a comprehensive way (also including its social dimension) and not only in a merely environmental sense.

2. Methodological note

The deliberative workshop was conducted on May 29, 2021. Given the persisting pandemic situation, even if the workshop was not organized in a period of particular restrictions, it was used the online format, hosting the dialogue on the Zoom platform. The workshop alternated moments of plenary discussion, moderated by a main facilitator, with moments of dialogue in smaller groups of 6 people (through breakout rooms), always moderated by a facilitator. The groups were each time re-sorted to allow a wider sharing of perspectives among all participants.

The duration of the workshop was 8 ½ hours total (9:30am-6pm), with a one-hour lunch break and two mid-morning and mid-afternoon half-hour breaks.

A sample of 18 citizens residing in Lombardy participated in the workshop, selected randomly but stratified by gender, province of residence and age. The size of the province had determined the presence of more people from some provinces. The distribution of participants is illustrated below:

Gender/Age	18-34	35-54	55 and over	Total
M	2	3	3	8
F	3	4	3	10
fTotal	5	7	6	18

LOMBARDY PROVINCE	
BERGAMO	2
BRESCIA	2
COMO	1
CREMONA	1
LECCO	1

LODI	1
MANTOVA	1
MILANO	4
MONZA E BRIANZA	1
PAVIA	1
SONDRIO	1
VARESE	2
Total	18

Even if the small number of participants cannot obviously be representative of the entire reference population involved in the deliberative exercise, the search for a diversity of voices, according to the parameters presented above, ensures heterogeneity of experiences and personal and professional paths, as well as geographical contexts, necessary for the success of these interventions of citizen engagement.

The recruitment of the 18 citizens was carried out by an agency specialized in qualitative surveys (Almar Qualitative Research). The same agency, in the costs of the service, has included a monetary incentive (given through PayPal) to the participants.

The workshop followed a structured format designed by Bassetti Foundation and moderated by the Bassetti Foundation team and an external professional facilitator.

The workshop followed the general "classic" format of deliberative dialogues:

- A first informative phase in which participants are introduced to the scope of the workshop, to the broader context (in this case the TRANSFORM project and the activities conducted within the Lombardy cluster) and to the focus on the topic, thanks also to the presence of experts with whom participants can interact with;
- A discussion phase to bring out the points of attention on the topic to be discussed;

- A final phase to formulate recommendations and consensus on the recommendations.

Below is the general schedule of the event (which has undergone some changes in terms of timing during the course of the event):

- 9.30 – 9.45 Greetings and brief introduction to the project/participatory process (plenary)
- 9.45 - 10.00 Introduction to the agenda, the "rules" and the topics of the day (plenary)
- 10.00 - 10.30 Short presentation of everyone - Ice breaker (plenary)
- 10.30 - 10.50 Presentations of the experts (plenary)
- 10.50 - 11.10 Preparation of questions to the experts (breakout rooms)
- 11.10 - 11.30 Questions to the experts (plenary)
- 11.30 - 12.00 BREAK
- 12.00 - 12.50 Energy transition in Lombardy: what to do? (breakout rooms). To start an energy transition in Lombardy what are the actions that could be taken? Clustering by macro-categories shared with group participants
- 12.50 - 13.30 Plenary discussion and selection of 3 macro-areas (plenary)
- 13.30 - 14.30 LUNCH BREAK
- 14.30 - 15.15 Fair energy transition for all in Lombardy (breakout rooms). For each macro issue selected, identify what can be the actions of social justice to be taken into account in grounding the actions for that macro-issue.
- 15.15 - 16.00 Discussion of the identified actions (plenary)
- 16.00 - 16.30 BREAK
- 16.30 - 17.15 Elaboration of recommendations to Lombardy Region for a fair energy transition for all in Lombardy (breakout room)
- 17.15 - 17.45 Plenary sharing and agreement on collective recommendations (plenary)
- 17.45 - 18.00 Survey and greetings (plenary)

As a conclusion to the workshop, participating citizens were asked to fill out a questionnaire prepared by the Bassetti Foundation. All participants completed the workshop evaluation questionnaire (see Chapter 8 for results).

3. The informative phase

In this first phase, the main facilitator illustrated the objectives of the day and the agenda of activities. Subsequently, she presented the TRANSFORM project and the activities of the Lombardy cluster, within which the participatory path and in particular the workshop are inserted, providing some more specific information on the energy transition subject.

The limited time with which the workshop was prepared did not allow for a broad recruitment of experts. The informative phase on the subject was therefore based on the display of a video interview⁴, available on the social media Youtube, with an Italian researcher among the most cited in the international literature as well as very well known in the dissemination of issues related to the energy transition, Nicola Armaroli, Director of Research at the CNR in Bologna. The choice fell on a name that was "foreign" to the Lombard context, certainly scientifically authoritative but also very experienced in communicating these issues to the public.

The informative phase was completed with the presence of the president of the Lombardy LE2C Cluster, Luca Donelli, who illustrated the possible options/technological solutions/research guidelines that the world of research/innovation (especially local) can put in place to facilitate energy transition.

Participants asked Luca Donelli some questions that have been prepared in the first workgroup in breakout rooms. The focus of the questions was mainly on the impacts of the energy transition on the work in the supply chain of non-renewable energy and on insights on the future prospects of hydrogen.

⁴ Interview with Nicola Armaroli by Il Bo Live: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vyjTJ5W--WQ>.

4. Energy transition in Lombardy: what to do?

In this first stage of work in the breakout rooms, the groups shared what they thought were the actions to be taken to initiate an energy transition in Lombardy. In each group, the various actions listed were clustered by the facilitator, in agreement with the participants, into macro-areas.

The sharing in the plenary then saw the presentation of all macro-areas by the 3 groups (and their sub-topics), namely:

- Citizen "energy transition" actions;
- Information and communication;
- Mobility actions;
- Better services and green incentives for public and private buildings;
- Actions for drinking water;
- Actions for waste disposal;
- Ecological school education;
- Job training and innovation;
- PA digitization;
- Research.

At the end of this session, participants were sent to vote, using the Zoom platform's polling features, on the 3 macro-areas considered a priority for them.

The result of the survey resulted in the choice of these 3 macro areas:

- Job training and innovation;
- Better services and green incentives for public and private buildings;
- PA digitization.

5. Fair energy transition for all in Lombardy

In the next phase, participants were asked to identify issues as well as "social justice" opportunities for each selected macro-area and possible responses, to prepare a basis for the subsequent development of recommendations.

In general, the macro-area Training and innovation in the work sector has identified the possible impacts of the energy transition in terms of the need to retrain workers impacted by depleting supply chains in the context of non-renewable energy, but also of opportunities, especially for younger people, for new green jobs, for which specific training is needed.

The macro-area Ecological services and incentives for public and private buildings has identified a huge problem of access (and before that of information) to existing incentives, with complex procedures that make it difficult for citizens to use the incentives, especially for those not expert in these issues.

Finally, the macro-area PA Digitization has gathered the attention of participants on the problem of the digital divide but especially of digital literacy of the older population.

6. Recommendations

The last stage of the workshop focused on the development of recommendations. Each group worked on two of the three macro-areas, followed by an overall integration in the plenary and the finalization of the collective consensus.

7. Final considerations in preparation of the next steps of citizen engagement

- The distinction between the different roles of institutions (national/regional/municipal level) on these issues is not always easily perceived by citizens. Many recommendations seem, in fact, to be addressed more to a national body, and some go beyond the role of governments at all levels. The regional government in the perception of the participants is (and should be) the impartial guarantor of the management of the entire path of energy transition and related impacts. A clearer delineation of room of maneuver of the different institutional levels would certainly help produce more "actionable" recommendations.
- The discussion has seen in several moments a rather accentuated polarization between the vision of the younger participants and those who represented or took charge of the needs of people of advanced age, often generating conflicting interests. The discussion of these issues will have to carefully consider these possible "intergenerational clashes", which are very present on issues of climate and sustainability that are generally issues that speak of the present, but necessarily lead into the near future.
- The results of the evaluation questionnaire also showed a desire for more information and more space for discussion on these issues. The problematization and discussion with citizens of relevant political choices such as the energy transition is a new approach in the Italian context, but well received by participants.
- None of the participants expressed that they were activists on these issues and this certainly brought attention to and discussion of the issues from unbiased points of view, thus bringing out new perspectives not coming from the so-called "usual suspects."

- Maintaining the focus on such a vast subject and with links to other issues of public interest, as also seen from the results of the survey of the previous phase (bureaucracy/digitization) is not an easy task, but not an unnecessary one in the context of a pilot workshop, which certainly served to sound out potential "hot" issues on the topic of fair energy transition for all in Lombardy. Similarly, it highlighted that the nexus digital-green deal is very present in the opinions of citizens and obviously in need of further unpacking and problematization, which digital technology entails, even in terms of sustainability.

Annex III - Smart and responsible mobility in Lombardy Region Citizens' Jury

Milan, 11th June 2022

Palazzo delle Stelline – Corso Magenta, 61

Agenda

10.00 - 10.30 Welcome Coffee

10.30 - 11.15 Introduction to the project and to the agenda of the day

Angela Simone - *EU H2020 TRANSFORM Project Coordinator, Bassetti Foundation*

Enza Cristofaro - *DG Education, University, Research, Innovation and Simplification, Lombardy Region*

Damiano Apicella - *Technical Management Board, EO15*

11.15 - 11.30 Coffee Break

11.30 - 13.00 Experts presentations - Group formulation and plenary question space

Francesco Lescai – *Associate Professor in Bioinformatics, Pavia University*

Francesca De Chiara - *Policy Leader Fellow, European University Institute*

13.00 - 14.00 Lunch

14.00 - 15.15 Expert presentation - Group formulation and plenary question space

Gianpiero Mastinu - *Full Professor of Vehicle Construction, Politecnico of Milano - Secretary General, Lombardy Mobility Cluster*

15.15 - 15.30 Coffee break

15.30 - 17.00 Experts presentations - Group formulation and plenary question space

Arda Lelo - *Professor of architectural history - Co-founder and vice president, Period think tank*

Gabriele Suffia - *Privacy expert in the context of smart-cities - PhD candidate in Science, Law and Technology, University of Bologna*

17.00 - 17.20 Plenary discussion on any topics citizens wish to study further

17.20 - 17.30 Conclusion of the day and greetings

Annex IV - Smart and responsible mobility in Lombardy Region Citizens' Jury

Milan, 25h June 2022

Palazzo delle Stelline – Corso Magenta, 61

Agenda

10.00 - 10.30 Welcome coffee

10.30 - 11.10 Introduction to the agenda of the day - **Angela Simone** (*Bassetti Foundation*)

11.10 - 13.00 Dialogue phase – plenary and groups (inside: coffee break)

13.00 - 14.00 Lunch

14.00 - 15.50 Deliberation phase I – plenary and groups

15.50 - 16.00 Coffee break

16.00 - 17.00 Deliberation phase II – plenary and groups

17.00 - 17.20 Presentation of collective recommendations to Lombardy Region representatives

17.20 - 17.30 Next steps and closing greetings - **Angela Simone** (*Bassetti Fo*)

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